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A larger augmented-reality field of view improves interaction with nearby holographic objects

Eva M. Hoogendoorn^{1*}, Daphne J. Geerse¹, Jip Helsloot¹, Bert Coolen¹, John F. Stins¹, Melvyn Roerdink^{1*}

¹Department of Human Movement Sciences, Faculty of Behavioural and Movement Sciences, Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam, Amsterdam Movement Sciences, Amsterdam, Netherlands

* Corresponding authors

E-mail: e.m.hoogendoorn@vu.nl (EH), m.roerdink@vu.nl (MR)

19 **Abstract**

20 Augmented-reality (AR) applications have shown potential for assisting and modulating gait in
21 health-related fields, like AR cueing of foot-placement locations in people with Parkinson's
22 disease. However, the size of the AR field of view (AR-FOV), which is smaller than one's own
23 FOV, might affect interaction with nearby floor-based holographic objects. The study's primary
24 objective was to evaluate the effect of AR-FOV size on the required head orientations for
25 viewing and interacting with real-world and holographic floor-based objects during standstill and
26 walking conditions. Secondary, we evaluated the effect of AR-FOV size on gait speed when
27 interacting with real-world and holographic objects. Sixteen healthy middle-aged adults
28 participated in two experiments wearing HoloLens 1 and 2 AR headsets that differ in AR-FOV
29 size. To confirm participants' perceived differences in AR-FOV size, we examined the head
30 orientations required for viewing nearby and far objects from a standstill position (Experiment
31 1). In Experiment 2, we examined the effect of AR-FOV size on head orientations and gait
32 speeds for negotiating 2D and 3D objects during walking. Less downward head orientation was
33 required for looking at nearby holographic objects with HoloLens 2 than with HoloLens 1, as
34 expected given differences in perceived AR-FOV size (Experiment 1). In Experiment 2, a greater
35 downward head orientation was observed for interacting with holographic objects compared to
36 real-world objects, but again less so for HoloLens 2 than HoloLens 1 along the line of
37 progression. Participants walked slightly but significantly slower when interacting with
38 holographic objects compared to real-world objects, without any differences between the
39 HoloLenses. To conclude, the increased size of the AR-FOV did not affect gait speed, but
40 resulted in more real-world-like head orientations for seeing and picking up task-relevant

41 information when interacting with floor-based holographic objects, improving the potential
42 efficacy of AR cueing applications.

43 **Introduction**

44 Leading augmented-reality (AR) glasses, like Microsoft HoloLens and Magic Leap, are
45 progressing towards consumer readiness, with profound improvements in wearer comfort, form
46 factor, data quality, and AR field of view (AR-FOV). One of the strengths of AR compared to
47 virtual reality is that the visible real world can be augmented with environment-aware digital
48 content, facilitating direct bodily interaction with digital objects. AR has therefore gained interest
49 in health-related fields like rehabilitation and physical therapy given its potential efficacy for gait
50 assistance [1, 2], gait modulation [3-5] gait-and-balance assessment [6-10] and gait-and-balance
51 training. In these fields, AR allows the user to experience the real world augmented with
52 (interactive) holographic floor-based objects like 2D AR cues to step onto or 3D AR obstacles to
53 step over, an action-relevant gait-guidance technique which could improve gait parameters like
54 stride length, step length and walking velocity in gait-impaired individuals [11-15].

55 In people with Parkinson's disease (PD), for example, AR has been explored for
56 providing external visual cues [1, 2]. External cueing (i.e., the use of external temporal or spatial
57 stimuli) is a well-established strategy for alleviating freezing of gait (FOG) and facilitating gait
58 in people with PD [16]. Visual cues were originally applied with 2D stripes taped to the ground
59 as targets for foot placement, but recent insights suggest that 3D cues, like an obstacle to cross,
60 could be more effective than 2D cues for modifying gait and alleviating FOG [17, 18]. By using
61 wearable AR glasses, such 2D or 3D holographic objects could be presented anywhere, anytime

62 instead of being location-bound as with real-world 2D or 3D cues, thereby potentially
63 broadening their applicability to everyday-life situations.

64 Geerse et al. examined the effect of 2D and 3D AR visual cueing using Microsoft
65 HoloLens 1 (see Fig 1A) on FOG in the home environment of people with PD [1]. Objective and
66 subjective immediate improvements in the number and duration of FOG episodes were found for
67 participants with long and/or many FOG episodes [1]. Participants reported that the wearer
68 comfort and the limited AR-FOV of HoloLens 1 ($30^{\circ} \times 17^{\circ}$ [19]) needed improvement [1], as they
69 experienced the holographic objects as if they were watching them through a relatively small,
70 rectangular screen, affecting the visibility of nearby AR objects (Fig 1A). Consequently,
71 relatively large downward head orientations were required to get nearby floor-based holographic
72 objects into view [1], see also [20-22]. This might limit the efficacy of AR cueing for alleviating
73 FOG and for assisting and modulating gait [1].

74 The second generation of Microsoft HoloLens, HoloLens 2, has a larger AR-FOV
75 ($43^{\circ} \times 29^{\circ}$ [19]; Fig 1B). The primary objective of this study was to systematically evaluate the
76 effect of AR-FOV size on the head orientation required for viewing and interacting with floor-
77 based real-world and holographic objects. The secondary objective was to evaluate the effect of
78 AR-FOV size on gait speed when interacting with floor-based real-world and holographic
79 objects. We invited a group of healthy, middle-aged adults (40-65 years) to participate in two
80 experiments. In Experiment 1 we compared the head orientation when looking, from a standstill
81 position, at floor-based real-world and holographic objects at various, nearby and far, distances
82 (Figs 2A-B, left panels). We expected a greater downward head orientation for looking at nearby
83 holographic compared to nearby real-world objects, but significantly less so for HoloLens 2 than
84 HoloLens 1 given its larger AR-FOV size. In Experiment 2 we compared the head orientations

85 when our participants were interacting with floor-based real-world and holographic 2D and 3D
86 objects onto a 6-meter walkway (Fig 2, all panels). Again, we expected a greater downward head
87 orientation in the vicinity of holographic compared to real-world 2D and 3D objects, but
88 significantly less so for HoloLens 2 than HoloLens 1 given its larger AR-FOV size. Based on
89 previous studies [3, 23], we expected that participants walked slightly slower when interacting
90 with holographic than with real-world objects, while we had no a-priori expectations on the
91 effect of AR-FOV size.

92 **Fig 1. Microsoft HoloLens 1 (A) and 2 (B) with a representation of their AR-FOV relative**
93 **to one's own FOV**

94 **Methods**

95 **Participants**

96 A convenience sample of 16 healthy middle-aged adults (mean [range]: 57 [46-65] years), of
97 which 6 females and 10 males, were included in the study. Participants had no conditions
98 interfering with gait function and no restrictions interfering with their depth perception or vision
99 (after potential corrective aids). Participants all provided written informed consent before
100 participation. The study was approved by the local Scientific and Ethical Review Board (VCWE-
101 2022-048).

102 **Experimental design and setup**

103 This n=16 convenience sample allowed for a full block-randomized counterbalancing of the
104 order of the experimental conditions. Specifically, all experiments comprised two experimental
105 factors with two levels each (hence yielding four possible orders): 1) Type of Object (real-world

106 or holographic) and 2) Type of HoloLens (HoloLens 1 or HoloLens 2) as our manipulation of
107 AR-FOV size (AR-FOV size of HoloLens 2 is greater than that of HoloLens 1; Table 1).
108 Holographic 2D and 3D objects were projected with the HoloLenses (Fig 2A). An overview of
109 the technical specifications of both devices is shown in Table 1. Real-world 2D objects were
110 presented with a projector (EPSON EB-585W, ultra-short-throw 3LCD projector; Fig 2B, left
111 and centered panels) while 3D objects comprised adjustable physical obstacles (Fig 2B, right
112 panel). HoloLens 1 and 2 were used to measure 3D head position and orientation in space,
113 wherein holographic and real-world content was aligned using spatial anchors and headset
114 position calibrated to real-world coordinates using a transformation matrix and predetermined
115 calibration positions. For all experiments, a 6-meter walkway with a width of 75cm was
116 projected, providing a floor-based canvas for presenting 1) 10 stepping stones (10×30cm with an
117 imposed step length of 60cm, where left and right stones were colored yellow and red,
118 respectively; Figs 2A-B, left panels), 2) a 2D stepping target (30×75cm, depth×width located
119 midway; Figs 2A-B, centered panels) and 3) a 3D obstacle (20×2cm, height×depth, located
120 midway; Figs 2A-B, right panels).

121 **Fig 2. Experimental setup.** (A) The 6-meter walkways with holographic objects as seen through
122 HoloLens and (B) real-world projected 2D or physical 3D objects on the floor.

123 **Table 1. Relevant device specifications of HoloLens 1 and 2.**

	HoloLens 1	HoloLens 2
Display	Optical see-through (OST) holographic lenses	Optical see-through (OST) holographic lenses
Holographic density	>2.5k radiants (light points per radian)	>2.5k radiants (light points per radian)
Holographic resolution	HD 16:9 light engines (1280 × 720)	2k 3:2 light engines (2048 × 1080)
AR-FOV	30° horizontal 17° vertical	43° horizontal 29° vertical
Sensors		
IMUs	Accelerometer, gyroscope, magnetometer	Accelerometer, gyroscope, magnetometer
Sampling frequency	30 Hz	30 Hz
Depth camera	1	1
Environment understanding camera	4	4
Human understanding		
Eye tracking	No	Yes, real-time
Hand tracking	Limited to gesture-based finger taps and basic palm moves	Two-handed fully articulated model, direct manipulation
Fit		
Weight	579 grams	566 grams, improved distribution

124

125 **Procedure**

126 Both headset conditions started with calibration of the HoloLens to participant’s interpupillary
 127 distance using Microsoft’s inbuilt calibration software [24] followed by a few minutes of
 128 habituation to HoloLens 1 or 2 (depending on the condition) and various holographic objects
 129 (i.e., for holographic objects conditions). To methodologically validate if participants perceived
 130 differences in the AR-FOV size, we quantified the number of visible real-world and holographic
 131 objects reported by our participants while wearing HoloLens 1 and 2. As expected, participants
 132 reported more real-world than holographic objects because the AR-FOV size is smaller than
 133 one’s own unobstructed FOV size (210°×150° [25]). However, the difference between the

134 reported real-world and holographic objects was significantly smaller for HoloLens 2 because its
135 AR-FOV size is greater than that of HoloLens 1 (Figs 1A-B). Participants thus noticed AR-FOV
136 size differences between HoloLenses. Subsequently, the two experiments were sequentially
137 performed in each condition.

138 **Experiment 1: head orientations for looking at real-world and holographic** 139 **objects**

140 We quantified the head orientation for looking, from a standstill position, at real-world and
141 holographic objects (i.e., stepping stones) onto the floor at various, nearby and far, distances.
142 Participants stood still and looked twice at every stepping stone in a predetermined random order
143 for 8 seconds. The number of the stepping stone which the participant should look at was
144 displayed on a screen next to the participant. Only the yellow stones were included, where the
145 first stone was the one closest to the participant (at 75cm along the walkway), and the fifth stone
146 was the most distant one (at 555cm along the walkway)(Figs 2A-B, left panels).

147 **Experiment 2: head orientation and gait speed for interacting with real-world** 148 **and holographic 2D and 3D objects during walking**

149 We quantified the head orientation and gait speed for interacting with real-world and holographic
150 2D and 3D objects while walking onto a 6-meter walkway. Participants were instructed to 1)
151 walk as precisely as possible over the sequence of stepping stones at a self-selected comfortable
152 speed (Figs 2A-B, left panels), 2) step onto a single 2D stepping target in the center of the
153 walkway (Figs 2A-B, centered panels), and 3) cross a 3D obstacle in the center of the walkway
154 (Figs 2A-B, right panels). For all three tasks, four trials were performed of which the first was

155 considered a practice trial. At the start and end of each trial, participants fixated straight ahead to
156 a red cross adjusted to their eye level to obtain their baseline head orientation.

157 **Data and statistical analysis**

158 Headset position and orientation data were recorded with either HoloLens 1 or 2 with a sampling
159 frequency of 30 Hz to analyze participants' head position along the line of progression on the
160 walkway (i.e., increasing along the walkway from the starting position) and head orientation in
161 terms of pitch (i.e., rotation of the headset along the lateral axis such that a downward rotation
162 corresponds to an increase in the orientation angle).

163 For Experiment 1, the median head orientation from 4-7s for looking at each stepping
164 stone separately was taken and averaged over the two repetitions for each stone (Fig 3A). In case
165 of data irregularities (e.g., high peaks due to sneezing during the trial or external distractions as
166 noted in the experimental logbook), the corresponding episode was excluded from analysis and
167 the median of the remaining episode was included for further statistical analysis. The head
168 orientation for the fifth stepping stone was regarded as the baseline, which was subtracted from
169 the other headset orientations to enable a fair comparison between HoloLens 1 and 2 in case of
170 variations over experimental conditions in the positioning of the AR display on the head relative
171 to the eyes. The resultant headset orientations were subjected to a $2 \times 2 \times 4$ (Type of Object \times Type
172 of HoloLens \times Stone [1 to 4]) repeated-measures ANOVA. The assumption of sphericity was
173 verified according to Girden [26]. If the Greenhouse-Geisser's epsilon exceeded 0.750, the
174 Huynh-Feldt correction was used. Otherwise, the Greenhouse-Geisser correction was applied.

175 For Experiment 2, baseline head orientation was again subtracted from the head-
176 orientation data for a fair comparison over experimental conditions. Head-orientation data were

177 then expressed as a function of distance along the walkway to enable comparing trials of
178 different durations within and between participants. A trial was excluded in case of data
179 irregularities (e.g., due to loss of spatial tracking for 2 out of 768 trials; there were always at least
180 two trials available per condition). The following task-specific outcome parameters were
181 derived, from which the median over repetitions was taken for further statistical analyses:

182 Continuous target-stepping task:

- 183 - The height of the characteristic initial peak, indicative of the *maximal initial downward*
184 *orientation* of the head to get the stepping stones in view at the start of the trial directly
185 after fixating at the cross at eye level (Fig 3B).
- 186 - The median head orientation between 2.0 and 4.0 meters, representing the *constant*
187 *downward* orientation required for performing the continuous target-stepping task (Fig
188 3B).
- 189 - The median *gait speed* (m/s) between 2.0 and 4.0 meters, calculated from the time
190 required to cover this 2-meter distance.

191 Incidental 2D target-stepping and 3D obstacle-crossing tasks

- 192 - The intercept and slope of the linear fit between the position and orientation of the
193 headset between 1.0 and 3.0 meters along the walkway (Fig 3C), the region where we
194 assumed participants oriented themselves towards the 2D stepping target and 3D
195 obstacle, representing *initial head orientation* and the *rate of change in head orientation*,
196 respectively.

197 - The median *gait speed* (m/s) for approaching the 2D stepping target or 3D obstacle
198 between 1.0 and 3.0 meters, calculated from the time required to cover this 2-meter
199 distance

200 Outcome parameters were again subjected to a 2×2 (Type of Object × Type of HoloLens)
201 repeated-measures ANOVA.

202 Effect sizes are reported as η_p^2 -values. Significant interactions were further explored
203 with paired-samples *t*-tests, focusing -considering the hypotheses- on differences between
204 HoloLenses for both real-world and holographic objects. All data underlying the statistical
205 analyses are available in S1 Table.

206 **Fig 3. Representation of head-orientation data for Experiments 1 and 2.** Looking from a
207 stand-still position at real and holographic objects at various, nearby and far, distances (A,
208 Experiment 1; stone numbers increase with distance) and negotiating a continuous sequence of
209 stepping targets (B, Experiment 2, continuous target-stepping task) as well as a single 2D
210 stepping target (C, Experiment 2, 2D target-stepping task). Higher values represent a more
211 downward head orientation. Head orientation was derived from the AR-headset orientation data,
212 normalized to the baseline head orientation.

213 **Results**

214 **Experiment 1: smaller downward orientation for seeing nearby** 215 **holographic objects with HoloLens 2 than with HoloLens 1**

216 As can be appreciated from Fig 3A, the head orientation varied with object distance in all four
217 conditions, with greater downward orientations for nearby stepping stones, supported by the

218 main effect of Stone ($F(1.55, 23.20)=1328.67, p<0.001, \eta_p^2=0.989$), with significant orientation
219 differences between all four stones ($p<0.001$). We expected a greater downward head orientation
220 for looking at nearby holographic compared to real-world objects, but less so for HoloLens 2
221 than HoloLens 1 given its larger AR-FOV size. This was indeed the case, as supported by the
222 three-way interaction ($F(2.07, 30.97)=14.59, p=0.045, \eta_p^2=0.191$). Post-hoc paired-samples t -
223 tests showed significant head-orientation differences between real-world and holographic objects
224 for most stepping stones, for both HoloLenses alike (Fig 4), notably in magnitude for the two
225 nearest objects. Head orientations for viewing any of the real-world stepping stones did not differ
226 between HoloLenses, while for holographic stepping stones -as expected- a significantly greater
227 downward orientation was required for HoloLens 1 than HoloLens 2, but only for the nearest
228 object (stone 1: $t(15)=3.377, p=0.004$). AR-FOV size thus mainly affected the orientation for
229 looking at nearby AR objects.

230 **Fig 4. Data visualization of Experiment 1.** * denotes a significant difference of $p<0.05$ between
231 conditions. ** denotes a significant difference of $p<0.001$ between conditions.

232 **Experiment 2**

233 **Smaller initial and constant downward orientations for negotiating a sequence** 234 **of stepping stones with HoloLens 2 than with HoloLens 1**

235 Head-orientation data showed statistically the same pattern of results over conditions for the
236 continuous target-stepping task. For both parameters (i.e., initial maximal peak and constant
237 orientation), a Type of Object \times Type of HoloLens interaction was found ($F(1,15)=11.33,$
238 $p=0.004, \eta_p^2=0.430$ and $F(1,15)=4.89, p=0.043, \eta_p^2=0.246$, respectively) on top of main effects
239 for Type of Object (greater downward orientation for holographic than for real-world objects;

240 $F(1,15)=66.86, p<0.001, \eta_p^2=0.817$ and $F(1,15)=84.83, p<0.001, \eta_p^2=0.850$, respectively) and
241 Type of HoloLens (greater downward orientation for HoloLens 1 than HoloLens 2 for the initial
242 peak only; $F(1,15)=24.09, p<0.001, \eta_p^2=0.616$ and $F(1,15)=0.28, p=0.604, \eta_p^2=0.018$,
243 respectively). In line with the results for nearby objects of Experiment 1, and as expected given
244 the larger AR-FOV for HoloLens 2 than for HoloLens 1, paired-samples *t*-tests revealed that the
245 initial maximal downward orientation (Fig 5A) as well as the constant downward orientation
246 (Fig 5D) for holographic stepping targets was significantly smaller for HoloLens 2 than for
247 HoloLens 1 ($t(15)=9.10, p<0.001$ and $t(15)=3.01, p=0.009$, respectively), in the absence of a
248 difference between HoloLenses for real-world stepping targets ($t(15)=0.63, p=0.535$ and $t(15)=-$
249 $1.00, p=0.332$, respectively).

250 **Smaller initial orientation and rate of change in downward orientation for** 251 **negotiating a single 2D stepping target or 3D obstacle with HoloLens 2 than** 252 **with HoloLens 1**

253 In line with our expectations, we found -by and large- a smaller initial orientation (i.e., intercept)
254 and rate of change in downward orientation towards the object (i.e., slope of the linear fit) for
255 HoloLens 2 than for HoloLens 1 when negotiating a 2D stepping target and a 3D obstacle. That
256 is, for the initial orientations (Figs 5B-C), we found a main effect of Type of Object for both the
257 2D target-stepping task ($F(1,15)=49.50, p<0.001, \eta_p^2=0.767$) and the 3D obstacle-crossing task
258 ($F(1,15)=23.56, p<0.001, \eta_p^2=0.611$), indicating a smaller initial orientation for interacting with
259 real-world than with holographic objects, aligning with the perception that the AR-FOV is
260 smaller than one's FOV. The main effect of Type of HoloLens was not significant for both tasks
261 (2D stepping target: $F(1,15)=0.76, p=0.398, \eta_p^2=0.048$; 3D obstacle crossing: $F(1,15)=2.64,$
262 $p=0.125, \eta_p^2=0.149$), while the Type of Object \times Type of HoloLens interaction was borderline

263 significant for 2D target-stepping ($F(1,15)=4.34, p=0.055, \eta_p^2=0.225$; Fig 5B) and 3D obstacle-
264 crossing ($F(1,15)=4.62, p=0.048, \eta_p^2=0.235$; Fig 4C) tasks, indicating that, at least for
265 holographic 3D obstacle crossing, the initial orientation was significantly smaller for HoloLens 2
266 than for HoloLens 1 ($t(15)=2.23, p=0.041$) in the absence of HoloLens differences for real-world
267 3D obstacles ($t(15)=-0.57, p=0.578$), a finding consistent with our expectations regarding the
268 difference in AR-FOV size between HoloLenses.

269 For the rate of change in downward orientation (Figs 5E-F), only a main effect of Type of
270 HoloLens was observed for the 2D target-stepping task ($F(1,15)=7.39, p=0.016, \eta_p^2=0.330$), in
271 the absence of main and interaction effects with the factor Type of Object ($F(1, 15)=0.55,$
272 $p=0.469, \eta_p^2=0.035$ and $F(1,15)=2.10, p=0.168, \eta_p^2=0.123$, respectively; Fig 5E) and any effect
273 for the 3D obstacle-crossing task (Type of HoloLens: $F(1,15)=0.19, p=0.669, \eta_p^2=0.013$; Type of
274 Object: $F(1,15)=0.29, p=0.596, \eta_p^2=0.019$; Interaction: $F(1,15)=1.17, p=0.296, \eta_p^2=0.072$; Fig
275 5F). This implied, consistent with our expectations regarding the difference in AR-FOV size
276 between HoloLenses, a significantly smaller rate of change in the downward orientation when
277 approaching the holographic 2D stepping target for HoloLens 2 than for HoloLens 1.

278 **Gait speeds are slightly slower for negotiating holographic than real-world** 279 **objects**

280 As expected, participants walked slower when negotiating holographic objects compared to real-
281 world objects, as supported by a significant main effect of Type of Object for the continuous
282 target-stepping and the 3D obstacle tasks ($F(1,15)=12.50, p=0.003, \eta_p^2=0.455$ and
283 $F(1,15)=11.34, p=0.004, \eta_p^2=0.431$, respectively; Figs 5G and I) and a borderline significant
284 difference for the 2D stepping-target task ($F(1,15)=4.48, p=0.051, \eta_p^2=0.230$; Fig 5H). For all
285 tasks, neither the main effect of Type of HoloLens (Continuous target stepping: $F(1,15)=1.18,$

286 $p=0.295$, $\eta_p^2=0.073$; 2D stepping target: $F(1,15)=1.91$, $p=0.187$, $\eta_p^2=0.113$; 3D obstacle:
287 $F(1,15)=0.26$, $p=0.621$, $\eta_p^2=0.017$) nor the Type of Object \times Type of HoloLens interaction
288 (Continuous target stepping: $F(1,15)=0.18$, $p=0.674$, $\eta_p^2=0.012$; 2D stepping target:
289 $F(1,15)=1.75$, $p=0.205$, $\eta_p^2=0.105$; 3D obstacle: $F(1,15)=2.57$, $p=0.130$, $\eta_p^2=0.146$) were
290 significant, indicating that AR-FOV size had no demonstrable effect on gait speed.

291 **Fig 5. Data visualization of Experiment 2.** Continuous target-stepping task (A, D, and G), 2D
292 stepping-target task (B, E, and H) and 3D obstacle-crossing task (C, F, and I). * denotes a
293 significant main effect of $p<0.05$ between conditions. ** denotes a significant main effect of
294 $p<0.001$ between conditions.

295 Discussion

296 The primary objective of this study was to evaluate the effect of AR-FOV size on head
297 orientations for viewing and interacting with floor-based real-world and holographic objects.
298 First, we observed, consistent with our expectations, a smaller downward head orientation when
299 looking at the nearest holographic stone with HoloLens 2 compared to HoloLens 1 (Experiment
300 1) in the absence of HoloLens differences when looking at the other three, more distant
301 holographic stones, probably because they become smaller and more centered in one's AR-FOV.
302 In Experiment 2, we found that a greater downward head orientation was required when
303 interacting with holographic than real-world 2D or 3D objects during walking, but significantly
304 less so for HoloLens 2 than HoloLens 1 because of its larger AR-FOV size. Results of 2D target-
305 stepping and 3D obstacle-crossing tasks do not match completely: in the 3D holographic
306 obstacle-crossing task the initial downward orientation was significantly smaller for HoloLens 2
307 than for HoloLens 1, whereas in the 2D target-stepping task the rate of change in downward

308 orientation was significantly smaller for HoloLens 2 than for HoloLens 1. Although in both tasks
309 the net result was a smaller downward head orientation with larger AR-FOV size, the
310 discrepancy over tasks in the effects of the complementary outcome parameters (i.e., smaller
311 initial orientation vs. smaller rate of change in downward orientation) probably hints at different
312 gazing strategies when approaching 2D vs. 3D sized objects and/or different gaze-fixation
313 patterns when negotiating targets vs. obstacles [27-29].

314 For the secondary objective, we evaluated the effect of different AR-FOV sizes on gait
315 speeds when negotiating holographic and real-world objects. Overall, participants walked
316 slightly slower when interacting with holographic objects compared to real-world objects (e.g., a
317 difference of 8.8 cm/s for the continuous target-stepping task representing a 0.14 seconds
318 difference over the calculated 2.0 meters)(Figs 5G-I). This finding is in line with previous
319 research [3, 23] where participants were suggested to walk more cautiously when approaching
320 holographic objects. No differences were observed between HoloLens 1 and 2, suggesting that
321 the gait speed was not influenced by the AR-FOV size.

322 This study was conducted in the broader context of AR applications for gait assistance
323 utilizing action-relevant floor-based 2D and 3D objects, like AR cueing for people with
324 neurological conditions like PD [1, 2]. In that regard, two observations are relevant that warrant
325 further investigation, as discussed next.

326 First, AR cueing may be related to the ecological-psychology concept of affordances
327 introduced by J.J. Gibson to refer to the action possibilities in the environment of an agent [30].
328 In the context of AR cueing, this environment is partly *mediated* by AR objects yielding
329 functional possibilities for action: 2D AR stepping targets afford to step onto, while a 3D AR
330 obstacle affords to step over. Such affordances exist by the detection of meaningful ecological

331 information from mediated environments. On the one hand, the limited AR display may
332 therefore have limited the availability of meaningful information from AR cues, yielding
333 suboptimal action opportunities, and hence potentially reducing the efficacy of AR cueing as
334 recently discussed [1, 2, 21]. Such reasoning matches with direct empirical proof that a smaller
335 AR-FOV size resulted in an underestimation of gap-stepping affordances [20]. On the other
336 hand, humans exploit a range of behaviors to extend the eye-brain connection by including
337 movements of the eyes, head, and body for revealing and picking up ecological information in
338 the optic array [31]. As E.J. Gibson [32] aptly put it: “*We don’t simply see, we look. The visual*
339 *system is a motor system as well as a sensory one. When we seek information in an optic array,*
340 *the head turns, the eyes turn to fixate, the lens accommodates to focus, and spectacles may be*
341 *applied and even adjusted by head position for far or near looking.*” This ecological-psychology
342 notion of perceptual systems may help in interpreting the effects of AR-FOV size on head
343 orientations. That is, downward head orientations are required and appropriate for the pickup of
344 ecological information from (mediated) environments to afford proper foot placement:
345 participants oriented their head more downwards when interacting with nearby objects, for real-
346 world and holographic objects alike, and appropriately changed their head orientation to pick up
347 ecological information in mediated environments, scaled to AR-FOV size. It remains to be seen
348 whether such changes in head orientations are sufficient for proper foot-placement (as afforded
349 by AR stepping stones or the AR 2D stepping target) and obstacle-crossing (as afforded by the
350 AR 3D obstacle) behaviors in mediated environments compared to gait modifications seen with
351 real-world counterparts (but see [5]).

352 Second, this study included healthy middle-aged adults instead of people with
353 neurological conditions like PD. This might be regarded as a limitation in the broader context of

354 AR cueing because whereas healthy individuals are known to use a feedforward mechanism
355 using exteroceptive information of the environment to plan proactive adjustments of gait [33],
356 people with PD have a stronger dependence on visual information for making online corrections,
357 often using conscious movement processing [34, 35]. Previous studies showed that visual cueing
358 aids the pickup of task-relevant information (including the perception of affordances) in people
359 with PD, improving safety of locomotion and foot-placement accuracy [36-38]. Together, this
360 indicates that a sufficient AR-FOV size might be even more important for interacting with floor-
361 based holographic objects for people with PD than for healthy individuals. Furthermore, a
362 limited AR-FOV size could promote an even more stooped posture in people with PD, which is
363 associated with poorer balance and an increased risk of falls, emphasizing the importance of a
364 sufficient AR-FOV size even more [39, 40].

365 Another limitation in the broader context of AR cueing is that we only examined the
366 effect of AR-FOV size on head orientations and performed gait speed, without examining
367 possible effects on gait modulation in terms of step length, cadence and obstacle-crossing heights
368 and lengths, which are relevant aspects for effective AR cueing. Future research with people with
369 PD is warranted to investigate if an increased AR-FOV size improves the efficacy of AR cues for
370 alleviating FOG and for assisting and modulating gait. Such studies may benefit from including
371 or comparing HoloLens 2 with other AR devices with an even larger AR-FOV size, like Magic
372 Leap 2 (45°×55° [41]) and the recently announced Meta Orion (with an AR-FOV expected to be
373 even larger). Alternatively, one could consider including a video see-through device (e.g., Apple
374 vision Pro) instead of only optical see-through devices as used in the current study, allowing for
375 more fine grained and wider evaluations of the effect of AR-FOV size on head orientation and
376 gait speed for interacting with nearby AR content. Video see-through devices, however, seem

377 less suitable for assisting and modulating gait in health-related fields, mainly because of the risk
378 of losing the vision of the real environment in case of system errors or an empty battery, which
379 could lead to dangerous situations in daily life as wearers then find themselves in a pitch-black
380 environment. Finally, studies may benefit from including eye-tracker data, present in state-of-
381 the-art AR headsets, to confirm the above-mentioned different gaze strategies associated with
382 negotiating targets vs. obstacles and/or 2D vs. 3D objects in real-world and AR environments.

383 To summarize, the downward head orientation was reduced for viewing and interacting
384 with holographic objects along the line of sight with HoloLens 2 compared to HoloLens 1,
385 particularly for objects nearby. Still, interacting with holographic objects required a somewhat
386 greater downward head orientation compared to interacting with real-world objects, which may
387 or may not affect affordance-based actions. Gait speed was not affected by AR-FOV size but was
388 slightly but significantly slower for negotiating holographic objects than real-world objects. The
389 ongoing technology development of AR devices will at least bring AR-FOV size closer to one's
390 FOV, from which AR applications for modulating and assisting gait in neurological conditions
391 like PD will probably benefit.

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515

516 **Supporting information**

517 **S1 Table. Data File.**